

Wireless and Cellular-Mobile Communication Architecture

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the generic GSM (global system for mobile communications) which consists of three subsystems: the Radio Subsystem (RSS), the Network Switching Subsystem (NSS), and the Operation Subsystem (OSS).

Keywords: radio subsystem, network switching subsystem, operation subsystem

1. Introduction

The global system for mobile communications (GSM) encompasses cellular networks for receiving and transmitting information.

2. Network Architecture of GSM

Figure 1. GSM Architecture.

The GSM network architecture is comprised of three subsystems (RSS, NSS, and OSS). The Radio Subsystem (RSS) is composed of the mobile terminals [mobile phone or mobile station (MS)] and Base Station Subsystem (BSS). The BSS is responsible for handling the mobile phone signaling including speech, text and video. Each BSS contains several cell/mobile phones, the Base Transceiver Station (BTS), and the Base Station Controller (BSC). The Transceiver (TRX) is a combination of a radio transmitter and receiver. The BTS is a fixed cell/mobile tower. The

BSC allocates radio channels, receives measurement from mobile devices, and controls BTS to BTS handover and call setup.

The Network Switching Subsystem (NSS) is a core component in GSN architecture that handles the switching of calls between external networks, for example, public switched telephone network (PSTN), and the BSCs in the radio subsystem. The NSS is comprised of the Mobile Switching Center (MSC), the Home Location Register (HLR), and the Visiting Location Register (VLR).

The Operation Subsystem (OSS) consists of the Operation and Maintenance Center (OMC), the Authentication Center (AuC), and the Equipment Identification Register (EIR). The OMC monitors and maintains the performance of each MS, BTS, BSC, and MSC. The OMC has three main functions: to maintain all telecommunications hardware and network operations; to manage all charging and billing procedures; and to manage all mobile equipment. The AuC generates and securely stores a shared secret known as the authentication key for each subscriber in the HLR. The EIR stores lists of International Mobile Equipment Identity (IMEI). The HLR is a database that store details relating to every cellphone number connected the GSM network across the world. The VLR is a database that contains the information about subscribers roaming within the MSC location area.

3. Conclusion

This article provides all the details and operations about the GSM architecture.